

Studies on Sowden-Fischer Nitromethane Synthesis

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Xylose was taken as the starting material for a Sowden-Fischer nitromethane condensation. A new type of product was obtained. This was proved by the method of periodate oxidation to be an anhydronitroalcohol.

A suspension of 15 g. of D-xylose in 100 ml of absolute ethanol and 40 ml of nitromethane was taken and to this added a solution of 3.3 g of sodium in 100 ml of absolute methanol. On shaking the sugar dissolved rapidly and a precipitate of the sodium salt of the anhydronitroalcohol was formed. The precipitate was shaken for five hours in a mechanical shaking machine to complete the reaction. The product was then cooled to 20° and filtered. The precipitate on the filter was washed rapidly with methanol and ether in the proportion 1:1, then ether and finally with petroleum ether. The resulting product was dissolved in 150 ml of water and then passed through a column containing 500 ml of washed Amberlite—1R-100; the column was washed off with 500 ml of water. The effluent was faintly acid. The product was concentrated at reduced pressure to a syrup. Then absolute ethanol was added twice, and the concentration repeated. 2ml of absolute ethanol was added to the syrup; it was then cooled and allowed to crystallize. 13.6 g. of the anhydronitroalcohol was obtained. It has m.p. 165° and $(\alpha)_D^{20} = 8.5^\circ$. The structure of the carbohydrate anhydronitroalcohol was proved by oxidation with sodium metaperiodate; it was found that 2.2 molecules of periodic acid were consumed per molecule of anhydronitroalcohol.

The structure of the anhydronitroalcohol is shown:

.1613 g of the anhydroalcohol was taken in a 25 ml flask and to it was added .163 molar NaIO_4 up to the mark. 5 ml of this solution was taken and to it was added 25 ml of .0107N

sodium arsenite solution. The resulting mixture required 14.7 c.c of 0.106*N* I₂ solution. Thus the total amount of periodate consumed is 0.395 g. Thus it is clear that 2.2 molecules of Na IO₄ are consumed per molecule of anhydronitro-alcohol.

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Received, November 15, 1967.